

1 **Mechanisms of SSRI resistance in man.**

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8 Selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors represent a significant advance in the treatment of anxiety and
9 depression in the community. We used induced pluripotent stem cell (IPS)-derived neurons from patients
10 responding to SSRIs or failing to respond to SSRI treatment to model SSRI resistance in stem cell culture
11 in and study the transcriptional basis SSRI treatment failure. We demonstrate here that in the iPS-derived
12 neurons of humans with MDD that fail to respond to SSRI antidepressant treatment, neurons activate the
13 cAMP regulated phosphoprotein 21 *ARPP5*. Additionally, we found silencing of the solute carrier
14 transporter *SLC35F3*. Importantly, SSRI-resistant neurons from humans with MDD activated both the
15 histamine receptor *HRH4* and the serotonin receptor *HTR7*. We present here transcriptomal evidence
16 outlining the molecular basis of SSRI resistance in man.

17 Citations

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